

EFIKASNOST SEKVENCIJALNOG ŠARŽNOG REAKTORA U TRETMANU KOMUNALNE OTPADNE VODE: PRELIMINARNI REZULTATI NA UKLANJANJE NEREGULISANIH ZAGAĐUJUĆIH SUPSTANCI

REMOVAL OF EMERGING CONTAMINANTS FROM MUNICIPAL WASTEWATER USING SEQUENCING BATCH REACTOR TECHNOLOGY: A PRELIMINARY RESULTS

IZVOD

Tretman otpadnih voda je neophodan za zaštitu zdravlja ljudi i životne sredine. Postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda (PPOV) moraju da se prilagode sve strožijim zahtevima za kvalitet efluenta, kako bi se postiglo uklanjanje širokog spektra zagađenja, poput različitih hemijskih supstanci i mikrobiološkog zagađenja. PPOV obezbeđuju da voda koja se ispušta iz postrojenja za prečišćavanje ispunjava regulatorne standarde za osnovne vrste zagađenja, kao što su masti, šećeri, proteini, nitrati, amonijak ili fosfati. Međutim, savremene analitičke metode pokazuju da PPOV nisu u mogućnosti da uklone neke vrste mikropolutanata, poput lekova, hormona, kontrastnih agenasa, veštačkih zaslađivača, narkotika, pesticida i dr. U radu su prikazani rezultati ispitivanja mogućnosti dva PPOV koja koriste tehnologiju sekvencijalnog šaržnog reaktora (eng. *Sequential Batch Reactor, SBR*) za uklanjanje mikropolutanata koji nisu regulisani, kao što su farmaceutski proizvodi i narkotici. Dobijeni podaci su pokazali da se neke supstance mogu vrlo efikasno ukloniti SBR tretmanom (npr. kofein, klaritromicin, teofilin, itd.), sa stopom uklanjanja većom od 90%, dok je za druge ovaj tretman neefikasan (npr. klindamicin-sulfoksid, sotalol, metadon, itd.). Da bi se postiglo bolje uklanjanje brojnih jedinjenja koja se koriste u svakodnevnom životu, potrebni su dodatni tretmani, koji mogu biti zasnovani na membranskim tehnologijama, unapređenim oksidacionim procesima, primeni novih adsorbenata i drugim metodama.

Ključne reči: tretman otpadnih voda, antibiotici, narkotici, SBR tretman

ABSTRACT

Wastewater treatment is necessary to protect human health and the environment, while wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) deal with a wide range of pollution, such as various chemical substances, microbial pollution, and also requirements for receiving water types, their possible management, and a gradually changing local climate. WWTPs ensure that the water discharged from treatment plants meets the regulatory standards for the basic types of pollution, such as fats, sugars, proteins, nitrates, ammonia, or phosphates. However, advanced analytical methods show that WWTPs are not able to remove some types of micropollutants, such as pharmaceuticals, drugs, hormones, contrast agents, artificial sweeteners, or pesticides. The present research investigates the possibilities of two WWTPs using a Sequential Batch Reactor (SBR) in removing micropollutants that are not on the regulatory lists. Obtained data showed that some compounds can be very efficiently removed by SBR treatment (e.g., caffeine, clarithromycin, theophylline, etc.), with the removal rate more than 90%, while for some compounds, the removal is not observed (e.g., clindamycin_sulfoxide, sotalol, methadone, etc.). In order to achieve better removal of numerous compounds used in everyday life, additional treatments are needed, which can be based on membrane technologies, advanced oxidation processes, new adsorbents, and others.

Keywords: wastewater treatment, emerging contaminants, antibiotics, drugs, SBR treatment

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1. UVOD

Tretman otpadnih voda u Evropi sprovodi se u skladu sa Direktivom EU o tretmanu urbanih otpadnih voda (eng. *EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive, UWWTD*), čiji je cilj zaštita zdravlja ljudi i životne sredine kroz obavezno sakupljanje i prečišćavanje otpadnih voda iz urbanih sredina koje bi inače mogle da zagađuju reke, jezera i mora. Ova direktiva ima ključnu ulogu u ostvarivanju ciljeva EU u okviru „Zelene agende za Evropu“, posebno kada je reč o postizanju nultog zagađenja, i pruža zaštitu kako ljudskom zdravlju, tako i vodenim ekosistemima.

Tretman otpadnih voda je od suštinskog značaja za očuvanje zdravlja ljudi i zaštitu životne sredine. Različita postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda (PPOV) širom Evrope suočavaju se sa širokim spektrom zagađenja, uključujući hemijska jedinjenja, mikrobiološko zagađenje, ali i izazove u pogledu kvaliteta recipijenata, njihovog upravljanja i postepeno promenjenih klimatskih uslova u lokalnim sredinama. Više od 90% komunalnih otpadnih voda u Evropi se sakuplja i tretira u skladu sa EU standardima. Među državama koje postižu više od 99% usklađenosti sa direktivom su Austrija, Nemačka, Luksemburg i Holandija. S druge strane, u zemljama poput Irske, Bugarske, Rumunije, Hrvatske i Malte, propisani standardi se primenjuju u manje od polovine urbanih područja (Malinauskaite i sar., 2024).

Tokom 2024. godine izvršena je revizija Direktive o urbanim otpadnim vodama, sa ciljem da se dodatno smanji zagađenje, potrošnja energije i emisija gasova sa efektom staklene bašte, da se poboljša kvalitet vode uklanjanjem preostalih izvora zagađenja iz urbanih otpadnih voda, unapredi pristup sanitaciji, posebno za ugrožene i marginalizovane grupe, i obezbedi da industrija snosi troškove tretmana mikropolutanata (EC Directive, 2024). Revidirana pravila nadovezuju se na tri decenije napretka, ali i odgovaraju na savremene izazove poput prisustva mikropolutanata, klimatskih promena i nejednakog pristupa sanitarnim uslugama. Uvođenjem strožijih standarda za tretman, proširenjem obaveza i na manje zajednice, kao i postavljanjem ambicioznih ciljeva za energetska neutralnost, nova direktiva trasira put ka zdravijim vodenim tokovima, otpornijoj infrastrukturi i cirkularnom pristupu upravljanju otpadnim vodama.

Za Srbiju, koja saraduje sa Evropskom agencijom za životnu sredinu, specifični podaci o tretmanu otpadnih voda su i dalje ograničeni. Iako Srbija nije članica Evropske unije i direktiva UWWTD se formalno ne primenjuje, ona može biti uključena u regionalne inicijative i projekte koji

1. INTRODUCTION

Wastewater treatment in Europe complies with the EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD), which aims to protect human health and the environment by ensuring that urban areas collect and treat wastewater that might otherwise pollute rivers, lakes, and seas. This directive plays a key role in supporting the EU towards the ambition of zero pollution, as set out in the European Green Deal, and protects human health and aquatic ecosystems.

Wastewater treatment is necessary to protect human health and the environment, while various wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in Europe deal with a wide range of pollution, such as various chemical substances, microbial pollution, but also requirements for receiving water types, their possible management, and a gradually changing local climate. More than 90% of municipal wastewater in Europe is collected and treated under EU standards. Countries that achieve over 99% compliance with the directive include Austria, Germany, Luxembourg, and the Netherlands. On the other hand, countries such as Ireland, Bulgaria, Romania, Croatia, and Malta meet the standards in less than half of their urban areas (Malinauskaite et al., 2024).

In 2024, there was the revision of the UWWTD Directive, which aims to reduce pollution, energy use and greenhouse gas emissions, improve water quality by addressing remaining urban wastewater pollution, improve access to sanitation, especially for the most vulnerable and marginalized groups, and ensure that industry paid for the treatment of micropollutants (EC Directive, 2024). The updated rules build on thirty years of progress while responding to pressing contemporary issues like micropollutants, climate change, and unequal access to sanitation. By introducing more rigorous treatment standards, extending requirements to smaller communities, and setting ambitious goals for energy neutrality, the directive sets a forward-looking course toward healthier waterways, more resilient infrastructure, and a circular approach to wastewater management.

For Serbia, which is one of the countries cooperating with the European Environment Agency, specific data on wastewater treatment are limited. Because Serbia is not a member of the EU, the UWWTD directive does not directly apply to Serbia, but it can be included in regional initiatives and projects aimed at improving water management and wastewater treatment within the wider region.

imaju za cilj unapređenje upravljanja vodama i tretmana otpadnih voda u širem regionu.

Uticaj klimatskih promena na količinu i kvalitet otpadnih voda, kao i na njihovo efikasno prečišćavanje, predstavlja važnu temu u kontekstu globalnog zagrevanja i zaštite životne sredine. Srbija, kao i druge zemlje Zapadnog Balkana, suočava se sa izazovima koje donose porast temperatura i sve učestalije i intenzivnije suše. Ove klimatske promene imaju značajan uticaj pre svega na poljoprivredu, dodatno povećavajući ranjivost zemlje s obzirom na njenu zavisnost od ovog sektora. Kao odgovor na ove izazove, unapređenje infrastrukture za tretman otpadnih voda mora postati prioritet, kako bi se efikasno rešavali problemi otpadnih voda i njihovi efekti na klimatske promene. Ulaganja u infrastrukturu, kao i saradnja sa međunarodnim partnerima, ključni su za napredak u ovoj oblasti.

Osnovni korak u planiranju i daljem razvoju postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda jeste sveobuhvatno razumevanje kvaliteta vode. U ovom radu predstavljeni su preliminarni rezultati ispitivanja efikasnosti *sekvencijalnog šaržnog reaktora* (SBR) u uklanjanju prisutnih zagađujućih materija, uključujući farmaceutske proizvode, hormone, proizvode lične higijene i njihove metabolite, kao i osnovne parametre kvaliteta vode (pH, elektroprovodljivost, hemijska potrošnja kiseonika (HPK), amonijak (NH₄-N), nitrati (NO₃-N) i fosfati (PO₄-P)). Dobijeni rezultati pružaju detaljan uvid u prisustvo osnovnih i specifičnih zagađujućih supstanci u analiziranim komunalnim otpadnim vodama.

2. MATERIJAL I METODE

Ispitivanja su vršena na postrojenjima za tretman otpadnih voda u dva manja mesta u Srbiji:

- Lokacija 1 - 7200 broj priključenih stanovnika i protok od 1650 m³/dan.
- Lokacija 2 - 2500 broj priključenih stanovnika i protok od 576 m³/dan.

Oba postrojenja primenjuju klasičan primarni tretman i sekundarni biološki tretman uz korišćenje SBR tehnologije. Uzorci sirove otpadne vode i efluenta sa oba postrojenja prikupljani su u intervalima od dva sata pomoću automatskog uređaja za uzorkovanje. Plan uzorkovanja bio je usklađen sa periodima najveće zagađenosti dolazne otpadne vode, kako bi se obezbedili reprezentativni podaci o opterećenju zagađujućim materijama i efikasnosti tretmana.

Uzorkovanje i analize obavljani su u martu 2024. godine. Uzorkovanje je sprovedeno u skladu sa standardima za uzorkovanje otpadnih voda (SRPS

The impact of climate change on the quantity and quality of wastewater and its effective treatment are important topics for contemporary Serbia in the context of global warming and environmental protection. Serbia, like other countries in the Western Balkans, faces challenges related to rising temperatures, which increase the frequency and intensity of drought. These climate changes have a major impact on agriculture in particular and increase the country's vulnerability due to its dependence on this sector. In response to these challenges, the upgrade of infrastructure for wastewater treatment in order to address wastewater issues and their effects on climate change must be prioritized. Investments in infrastructure and cooperation with international partners are key to progress in this area.

A fundamental step in the planning and further development of a wastewater treatment plant is gaining a comprehensive understanding of water quality. This paper presents preliminary results from monitoring the efficiency of a sequencing batch reactor (SBR) in removing emerging contaminants, including pharmaceuticals, hormones, personal care products, and their metabolites, etc., along with some general water quality parameters (pH, electroconductivity, chemical oxygen demand (COD), ammonia (NH₄-N), nitrates (NO₃-N) and phosphates (PO₄-P). The findings provide a detailed overview of both basic and specific pollutants present in the investigated municipal wastewaters.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two smaller WWTPs in Serbia were selected for the investigation:

- Location 1 - 7200 connected inhabitants and a flow rate of 1650 m³/day.
- Location 2 - 2500 connected inhabitants and a flow rate of 576 m³/day.

Both plants use classical primary treatment and secondary biological treatment with SBR technology. Influent and effluent samples from both facilities were collected at two-hour intervals using an automatic sampling device. The sampling schedule was designed to coincide with peak pollution periods in the incoming wastewater, ensuring representative data on contaminant loads and treatment performance.

Sample collection and analysis were conducted in March 2024. Sampling was conducted according to standard methods for sampling of wastewater (SRPS EN ISO 5667-1:2023). The samples were transported to the laboratory and stored at 4 °C until analysis.

ISO 5667-10:2021, SRPS EN ISO 5667-1:2023). Uzorci su transportovani do laboratorije i čuvani na temperaturi od 4 °C do analize.

Analizirani su sledeći parametri: pH, elektroprovodljivost, hemijska potrošnja kiseonika (HPK), amonijak ($\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$), nitrati ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) i fosfati ($\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$). pH vrednost određena je pomoću pH metra METTLER TOLEDO FiveEasy Plus FP20-Std-Kit (SRPS H.Z1.111:1987). Elektroprovodljivost je određena konduktometrom Hanna, model HI 933000 (Austrija), Cond 3210 sa elektrodama Tetracon 325 WTW (SRPS EN 27888:2009). HPK u vodi određena je u skladu sa metodom SRPS ISO 6060:1994. Koncentracija amonijaka određena je prema metodi SRPS ISO H.Z1.184:1974. Nitrati su određeni spektrofotometrijskom metodom u skladu sa standardnom metodom (SRPS ISO 7890-3:1994). Koncentracije ortofosfata određene su spektrofotometrijski primenom amonijum-molibdata, u skladu sa metodom SRPS EN ISO 6878:2008.

Za analizu organskih jedinjenja od interesa, uzorci su prethodno obrađeni i analizirani pomoću LC-MS/MS i Orbitrap uređaja. Analizirano je preko 100 farmaceutskih proizvoda, narkotika i njihovih metabolita. Uzorcima (10 ml homogenizovanog i filtriranog uzorka preko GFC filtera, 0,45 μm) dodavani su izotopski obeleženi interni standardi. Tako pripremljeni uzorci analizirani su SPE HPLC sistemom u kombinaciji sa hibridnim kvadrupolom (Orbitrap) – ultraosetljivim masenim spektrometrom. Ova procedura omogućava kvantitativnu analizu ciljnih jedinjenja i njihovih metabolita u koncentracijama reda veličine ng/l.

3. REZULTATI I DISKUSIJA

3.1. Efikasnost SBR tretmana u uklanjanju organskih materija i nutrijenata iz komunalnih otpadnih voda

Analize otpadnih voda ključne su za procenu kvaliteta vode i efikasnosti tretmana. Vrednosti parametara poput HPK, sadržaja nitrata, amonijaka i fosfata važne su za određivanje prisustva organskih zagađujućih materija, kao i koncentracija nutrijenata koji mogu doprineti eutrofikaciji površinskih voda. Za analizu ovih parametara najčešće se koriste spektrofotometrijske metode, koje omogućavaju precizno i brzo merenje, čime se značajno unapređuju monitoring i upravljanje radom postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda. Metodologija analize obuhvata pripremu uzoraka, kalibraciju instrumenata i merenje pomoću specifičnih reagenasa za pojedinačne analite.

The following parameters were measured: pH, electroconductivity, chemical oxygen demand (COD), ammonia ($\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$), nitrates ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$), and phosphates ($\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$). The pH of the samples was measured using a METTLER TOLEDO FiveEasy Plus pH meter FP20-Std-Kit (SRPS H.Z1.111: 1987). Electrical conductivity was analyzed using a Hanna conductometer, model HI 933000, Austria, Cond 3210 with a Tetracon 325 WTW electrode. COD in water was determined according to the SRPS ISO 6060:1994 method. Ammonia concentration in water was determined using the SRPS ISO H.Z1.184:1974 method. Nitrates in water were determined according to the SRPS ISO 7890-3:1994 method. Orthophosphate concentrations in water were determined spectrophotometrically with ammonium molybdate according to the SRPS EN ISO 6878:2008 method.

For the organic compounds of interest, samples were pretreated and analyzed using an LC-MS/MS and Orbitrap device (over 100 pharmaceuticals, drugs, and their metabolites were analyzed). Isotopically labelled internal standards were added to 10 ml of homogenized and filtered (GFC filter, 0.45 μm) sample. Samples pretreated this way were analyzed in an SPE HPLC system in tandem with a hybrid quadrupole (Orbitrap) – ultra-sensitive mass spectrometer. This procedure makes it possible to quantitatively analyze selected substances or their metabolites in wastewater in concentrations of ng/l units.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. SBR treatment efficiency in the organic matter and nutrients removal from municipal wastewater

Wastewater analyses are key to assessing water quality and treatment efficiency. Values such as COD (chemical oxygen demand), $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ (nitrates), $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ (ammonium), and $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ (phosphates) are important for determining the amount of organic pollutants as well as nutrient concentrations that can contribute to eutrophication in surface waters. For the analysis of these parameters, photospectrometers are most often used, allowing accurate and fast measurement of these parameters, which makes the monitoring and management of the purifiers more efficient. Analysis methodology includes sample preparation, instrument calibration, and measurement using specific reagents for individual analytes.

The influent and effluent from selected treatment plants were analyzed for the parameters COD, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, and $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ using Hach Lange sets and the DR 6000 device. Hach Lange sets were chosen according

Tabela 1: Osnovne analize otpadnih voda

Parametar	Lokacija 1 – sirova otpadna voda	Lokacija 1 – efluent	Lokacija 2 – sirova otpadna voda	Lokacija 2 – efluent
NH₄-N (mg/l)	74,30	21,60	36,40	0,076
NO₃-N (mg/l)	2,15	0,552	10,2	1,96
PO₄-P (mg/l)	9,41	9,54	2,80	0,794
HPK (mg/l)	515	308	278	218

Table 1: Basic wastewater analyses.

Parametar	Location 1 – raw wastewater	Location 1 – effluent	Location 2 – raw wastewater	Location 2 – effluent
NH₄-N (mg/l)	74.30	21.60	36.40	0.076
NO₃-N (mg/l)	2.15	0.552	10.2	1.96
PO₄-P (mg/l)	9.41	9.54	2.80	0.794
COD (mg/l)	515	308	278	218

Rezultati analize otpadnih voda i efluenata iz odabranih postrojenja za tretman otpadnih voda prikazani su u Tabeli 1.

Dobijeni rezultati analize osnovnih parametara otpadnih voda iz postrojenja za tretman otpadnih voda na lokacijama 1 i 2 ukazuju na ograničenu sposobnost ovih postrojenja da uklone ukupno organsko zagađenje i amonijak. Nitrati se na oba postrojenja uklanjaju sa zadovoljavajućom efikasnošću, dok se fosfor uspešno uklanja samo na lokaciji 2. Međutim, važno je napomenuti da su dobijeni rezultati zasnovani na uzorcima koji nisu 24-časovni kompozitni uzorci, što može biti razlog za uočene vrednosti zagađenja, naročito u efluentima posmatranih postrojenja.

3.2 Analiza farmaceutskih proizvoda i narkotika

Na slikama 1 i 2 predstavljeni su rezultati analiza farmaceutskih proizvoda i narkotika, kao i njihovih metabolita u otpadnim vodama i efluentima sa ispitivanih PPOV. U otpadnim vodama prisutan je širok spektar farmaceutskih proizvoda i narkotika ili njihovih metabolita, uključujući nesteroidne antiinflamatorne lekove, lipide-modifikujuće agense, diuretike, beta-blokatore i druge farmaceutske i proizvode za ličnu negu. Ove supstance obuhvataju aktivne farmaceutske sastojke kao što su antibiotici, analgetici, regulatori krvnih lipida, prirodni i sintetički hormoni, antidiabetici i antihipertenzivi. Njihovo prisustvo u otpadnim vodama posledica je ispuštanja iz domaćinstava, bolnica, industrijskih objekata i drugih izvora (Lozano et al., 2022).

to whether the influent or effluent was analyzed (e.g., value range COD was 150-2000 mg/l and 0-150 mg/l). The results are summarised in Table 1.

The obtained results of the analysis of the basic parameters of wastewater from the treatment plants at Location 1 and Location 2 point to the limited ability of the treatment plants to remove total organic pollution and ammonia. Nitrates are removed at both treatment plants with sufficient efficiency, and phosphorus only at Location 2. However, the achieved results are obtained from samples that are not 24-hour poured samples, which may be the reason for these wastewater values, especially in the effluent from the monitored treatment plants.

3.2 Analysis of pharmaceuticals and narcotics

A wide variety of pharmaceuticals and drugs or their metabolites are present in wastewater, including nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, lipid-modifying agents, diuretics, beta-blockers, and other pharmaceutical and personal care products (PPCPs). These substances include active pharmaceutical ingredients such as antibiotics, analgesics, blood lipid regulators, natural and synthetic hormones, antidiabetics, and antihypertensives. Their presence in wastewater is a consequence of their discharge from households, hospitals, industrial facilities, and other sources. Although these substances can be present in concentrations ranging from nanograms to milligrams per litre, traditional cleaning methods are often not effective enough to completely remove them (Lozano et al. 2022). WWTPs play a

Iako se ove supstance javljaju u koncentracijama koje variraju od nanograma do miligrama po litru, tradicionalne metode prečišćavanja često nisu dovoljne da ih u potpunosti uklone. Postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda imaju ključnu ulogu u smanjenju sadržaja PPCPs u otpadnim vodama, ali njihova efikasnost u uklanjanju ovih zagađujućih supstanci varira. Na primer, sistemi sa membranskim bioreaktorima pokazali su veću efikasnost u uklanjanju nekih farmaceutika, dok su supstance kao što su karbamazepin i hidrohlorotiazid uklonjene sa nižom efikasnošću. Takođe, ukazano je da su neki lekovi, poput atenolola, venlafaksina, oksazepama i karbamazepina, otporni na degradaciju u kanizacionom sistemu (Loganathan i sar., 2023).

Ovo ukazuje na potrebu za dodatnim, često naprednijim metodama prečišćavanja, poput naprednih oksidacionih procesa ili adsorpcije korišćenjem inovativnih sorbenata, kako bi se farmaceutski proizvodi efikasno uklonili. Uticaj PPCPs na vodene ekosisteme izaziva brojne zabrinutosti, jer mogu štetiti vodenim organizmima i doprineti razvoju antimikrobne rezistencije. PPCPs se mogu akumulirati u sedimentima i ulaziti u hranidbene lance, sa potencijalno dugoročnim negativnim posledicama po životnu sredinu. Iako su neki PPCPs biorazgradivi, mnogi su otporni na degradaciju, mogu dugo opstajati u životnoj sredini i kontaminirati podzemne vode (Wilkinson i sar., 2024).

Rezultati monitoringa više od 100 farmaceutskih proizvoda i lekova ili njihovih metabolita u otpadnim vodama iz odabranih postrojenja pokazuju odličnu sposobnost postrojenja za uklanjanje određenih mikropolutanata, sa efikasnošću većom od 90%. To su uglavnom supstance poput kofeina, kokaina, cetirizina, klaritromicina, teofilina i benzoilekgonina (lekovi i njihovi metaboliti, antibiotici, antihistaminici). Međutim, značajan deo ovih mikropolutanata uklanja se sa efikasnošću od oko 50 % ili manje na oba postrojenja. To su uglavnom metaboliti lekova kao što su karbamazepin – trans-dihidro-dihidroksi CBZ i metoprolol kiselina, ali i lekovi poput sertralina, morfina, mirtazapina, kodeina, alprazolama, valsartana, telmisartana, rozuvastatina, metoprolola, hidrohlorotiazida, diklofenaka, bisoprolola i azitromicina.

Kao što se može videti, radi se o hemijski i funkcionalno različitim vrstama supstanci. Među njima su lekovi iz grupe opioida i neopiodnih analgetika, lekovi za kardiovaskularne bolesti i antibiotici. U poslednjoj grupi farmaceutika i narkotika, neke supstance se uopšte ne uklanjaju u postrojenjima ili se čak primećuje povećanje njihove koncentracije u efluentu. Ovo je posledica njihove

key role in reducing PPCPs in wastewater, but their effectiveness in removing these contaminants often varies. For example, while membrane bioreactor systems showed higher efficiency in removing some pharmaceuticals, substances such as carbamazepine and hydrochlorothiazide were removed with lower efficiency. In addition, it has been pointed out that some drugs, such as atenolol, venlafaxine, oxazepam, or carbamazepine, appear to be resistant to degradation in the sewage system. This suggests that additional, often more advanced, purification methods such as advanced oxidation processes or adsorption using innovative sorbents may be necessary for the effective removal of pharmaceuticals (Loganathan et al., 2023). The impact of PPCPs on aquatic ecosystems is currently the subject of various concerns, as they may harm aquatic organisms and may contribute to antimicrobial resistance. PPCPs can accumulate in sediments and enter food webs, with potential long-term negative environmental consequences. Although some PPCPs are biodegradable, many are resistant to degradation and can persist in the environment for long periods, and contaminate groundwater (Wilkinson et al. 2024).

The achieved monitoring results of more than 100 pharmaceuticals and drugs or their metabolites in wastewater from selected treatment plants show the excellent ability of the treatment plants to remove some types of these micropollutants (efficiency over 90 %). These are mainly selected substances such as caffeine, cocaine, cetirizine, clarithromycin, theophylline, and benzoylecgonine (drugs and their metabolites, antibiotics, antihistamines). However, a significant part of these types of micropollutants at both treatment plants is removed with an efficiency of around 50 % and lower. These are mainly metabolites of drugs such as carbamazepine - trans-dihydro-dihydroxy CBZ and metoprolol acid, but also drugs such as sertraline, morphine, mirtazapine, codeine, alprazolam, valsartan, telmisartan, rosuvastatin, metoprolol, hydrochlorothiazide, diclofenac, bisoprolol, or azithromycin. As can be seen, these are chemically and functionally different types of substances/drugs. These include medicines from the group of opioid and non-opioid analgesics, medicines for cardiovascular diseases, and antibiotics. In the last group of pharmaceuticals and drugs, some substances are not removed at all at the treatment plants, or we even observe an increase in their concentration in the drain. This is caused only by their limited ability of sorption to sludge, biological degradation, or photodegradation.

The increase in concentration can be caused by the very concentration of substances in the sludge in

Slika 1. Koncentracije farmaceutskih proizvoda i njihovih metabolita u sirovoj otpadnoj vodi i efluentu postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda

Figure 1. Concentrations of pharmaceuticals in the raw wastewater and WWTP effluent

ograničene sposobnosti sorpcije na mulj, biološke razgradnje ili fotodegradacije.

Povećanje koncentracije određenih supstanci može biti uzrokovano njihovim zadržavanjem u mulju tokom bioloških procesa prečišćavanja, razlaganjem tzv. matičnih supstanci u kanalizacionom sistemu i u samom postrojenju (hemijski srodne supstance

biological cleaning processes, by the splitting of the so-called parent substances in the sewage system and at the treatment plant (chemically related substances or metabolites) but also by taking a sample when we did not implement a 24-hour poured sample (this is due to the absence of an automatic sampling device, which may not be present at smaller treatment

Slika 2. Koncentracije drugih mikropolutanata detektovanih u sirovoj otpadnoj vodi i efluentu postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda

Figure 2. Concentrations of other emerging contaminants in the raw wastewater and WWTP effluent

ili metaboliti), ali i činjenicom da uzorci nisu bili 24-časovni kompozitni uzorci (što je posledica nepostojanja automatskog uzorkivača, koji često nedostaje u manjim postrojenjima).

U pitanju su jedinjenja ili metaboliti lekova kao što su klindamicin i njegov metabolit klindamicin-

plants). These are compounds or metabolites of drugs such as clindamycin and the metabolite clindamycin_sulfoxide, O-Desmethyltramadol, venlafaxine and O-Desmethylvenlafaxine, irbesartan, sotalol or methadone. These medicines or drugs and their metabolites penetrate surface and underground

sulfoksid, O-desmetiltramadol, venlafaksin i O-desmetilvenlafaksin, irbesartan, sotalol ili metadon. Ovi lekovi i njihovi metaboliti mogu dospeti u površinske i podzemne vode. Njihova toksičnost po vodene ekosisteme često nije u potpunosti poznata.

Kofein se najčešće detektuje u površinskim vodama, iako se dobro razgrađuje u postrojenjima za prečišćavanje, njegova visoka koncentracija u ulaznoj vodi može dovesti do prisustva u recipijentima. Diklofenak, koji je toksičan za ptice jer se prenosi kroz lanac ishrane (npr. preko riba), oksazepam, koji utiče na ponašanje riba, i karbamazepin, koji se akumulira u organima riba, predstavljaju dodatni razlog za zabrinutost kada je reč o emergentnim zagađujućim materijama u vodenoj sredini.

4, ZAKLJUČAK

Rezultati ukazuju na to da postrojenje za tretman otpadnih voda uklanjaju većinu ispitivanih zagađujućih supstanci manje od 50%, tokom konvencionalnog tretmana otpadnih voda pomoću SBR tehnologije. Ipak, visoka efikasnost uklanjanja (preko 90%) zabeležena je za određene jedinjenja, uključujući kofein, kokain, cetirizin, klaritromicin, teofilin i benzoilekgonin.

Značajno je napomenuti da su pojedine supstance uklonjene samo minimalno, a u nekim slučajevima je čak uočeno povećanje njihove koncentracije u efluentu, što može ukazivati na procese desorpcije, transformacije u okviru biološkog sistema ili varijacije u analitičkom merenju.

Ovi nalazi jasno ukazuju na ograničenja konvencionalnih metoda prečišćavanja u efikasnom uklanjanju širokog spektra mikropolutanata i naglašavaju potrebu za integracijom unapređenih tehnologija tretmana, kako bi se postiglo sveobuhvatnije uklanjanje ovih supstanci.

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waters. Their toxicity to the aquatic ecosystem is often unknown. Caffeine is most often found in surface waters (it has good degradability at the WWTP, but the amount in the inflow often causes its presence in surface waters), diclofenac (toxic to birds - passes through the food chain, e.g. from fish), oxazepam (affects the behaviour of fish) or carbamazepine (concentrates in fish organs).

4. CONCLUSION

The results indicate that the majority of the emerging contaminants investigated exhibit removal efficiencies below 50% during conventional wastewater treatment using SBR technology. However, high removal efficiencies (exceeding 90%) were observed for specific compounds, including caffeine, cocaine, cetirizine, clarithromycin, theophylline, and benzoylecgonine.

Notably, certain substances were only minimally removed, and in some instances, their concentrations increased in the treated effluent, suggesting potential desorption, transformation, or analytical variability.

These findings underscore the limitations of conventional treatment processes in effectively eliminating a broad spectrum of micropollutants and highlight the necessity of integrating advanced or tertiary treatment technologies to ensure more comprehensive removal.

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